

Efficient Demand Management For The On-Time Arrival Problem: A Convexified Multi-Objective Approach Assuming Macroscopic Traffic Dynamics

C. Menelaou, S. Timotheou, P. Kolios and C.G. Panayiotou

Abstract—This work proposes a novel solution approach to address the On-Time Arrival (OTA) problem, considering macroscopic traffic dynamics. In this context, all drivers who intend to use the road infrastructure are required to communicate their origin-destination pair and desired arrival time to a central scheduler prior to starting their trip. In response, the scheduler assigns a departure time and a multi-regional route to each driver to make possible their on-time arrival at the destination. The OTA problem is formulated as a nonconvex, nonlinear, multi-objective optimization problem considering two objective criteria. The first criterion aims at minimizing the travel time of all drivers in the network to prevent congestion, while the second criterion seeks to minimize the discrepancy between the desired and actual arrival time. The proposed formulation is solved efficiently through an approximated convex solution that leverages the Normal Boundary Intersection (NBI) method to efficiently generate a representative sample of the Pareto Front. Additionally, two solution methodologies based on “knee” solution and the Nash Bargaining Game is proposed which can be used to select a unique solution across all the Pareto points, that offers a reasonable trade-off between the two objective criteria. Finally, simulation results demonstrate that the proposed solution can significantly reduce congestion while ensuring that most drivers will arrive at their destination on their desired time.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traffic congestion represents a significant challenge that modern societies face. This issue arises primarily because many drivers attempt to use the same part of the road infrastructure simultaneously [1]. To address this problem, various traffic management schemes have been proposed. For instance, Route Guidance strategies [2], [3] aim to distribute traffic loads across the network by guiding drivers to alternative routes, thereby improving overall travel times. Similarly, Perimeter Control and Gating approaches [4], [5], [6] strive to prevent congestion by restricting the inflow rate of vehicles at the periphery of a protected region. While these strategies help maintain congestion-free levels within

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the protected area, they also pose a risk of creating long queues at its boundaries.

Despite the remarkable technological advancements and the plethora of traffic management schemes available today, traffic congestion remains a persistent problem [7] that is expected to be worsen. The main reason for this is that the majority of management schemes are focused on improving the needs of individuals rather than the system optimum [8]. However, recent research has demonstrated that an effective way to address traffic congestion is through the integration of traffic and demand management strategies [9]. By combining these approaches, traffic flows can be redistributed in both time and space domains to optimize the overall system performance [10]. This joint approach can help to eliminate traffic congestion and improve the efficiency of the urban transportation systems [11].

Traffic demand management strategies primarily aim to manage the inflow rate of vehicles into the network by influencing drivers to choose earlier/late trip departure times or alternative modes of transport [12]. Similarly, several demand management approaches have been introduced for the On-Time Arrival (OTA) problem, many of which are combined with route guidance [11].

The OTA problem is concerned with determining optimal departure times and routes for drivers, such that the likelihood of their on-time arrival is maximized while minimizing the risk of arriving too early or too late at their destination [13]. Interestingly, routing decisions can be made using either stochastic or deterministic link traversing times [14]. In the latter case, each link (road segment) is represented by a random variable with an associated probability distribution for the travel time [15]. However, these approaches may be impractical for real-life implementations due to their high computational complexity [16].

An alternative approach is to consider macroscopic traffic dynamics [16]. Macroscopic dynamics are expressed using the three traffic parameters of speed, flow, and density, which are used to construct the Macroscopic Fundamental Diagram (MFD) [17]. Various traffic management techniques have been proposed based on the concept of the MFD, such as multi-regional route guidance, where vehicles are directed to follow multi-regional routes [3]. Recently, many efforts have focused on using macroscopic traffic dynamics for demand management purposes, as in the work presented in [18], which developed a multi-regional demand management method to shift drivers' departure times.

MFD-based schemes that follow aggregated dynamics result in nonconvex nonlinear optimization problems [18]. As a result, their real-time application is still impractical, as solving nonconvex optimization problems using standard nonlinear solvers is computationally expensive and yields sub-optimum control decisions.

To tackle the computational challenges associated with MFD-based schemes, our previous work in [19] presents a convex optimization framework that approximates all nonlinear dynamics, thereby enabling the integration of demand management with route guidance in real-time applications. Complementing this, [9] introduce an MFD-based strategy for the Optimal Traffic Assignment (OTA) problem. Nonetheless, while this strategy is designed to tackle a multi-objective formulation, its reliance on the weighted-sum scalarization method [20] results in a suboptimal generation of the Pareto Front, thereby limiting its applicability. In light of these limitations, this work presents a new formulation for the OTA problem, paired with a solution approach that is capable of effectively generating the Pareto Front and also introduces a methodology for selecting an efficient solution across all the potential solutions available along the Pareto.

Specifically, this work proposes a multi-objective formulation for the OTA problem that considers macroscopic traffic dynamics. The objective is to minimize the difference between the actual and desired arrival times for each OD pair and at the same time to avoid the emergence of congestion. To generate a representative sample of the Pareto front, the Normal Boundary Intersection (NBI) method is used, which employs a scalarization technique that leads to generation of a near-uniform spread of the Pareto points. To ensure computational efficiency, a convex formulation of the NBI that approximates all nonlinear nonconvex constraints with convex ones is proposed. Additionally, this work introduces a methodology for identifying a single Pareto optimal solution based on the Nash bargain theory [21]. The Nash bargain solution identifies the Pareto point that maximizes the product of the net benefit of the two conflicting objective functions, enabling the identification of the “best” Pareto solution by solving a single optimization problem over all the points of the Pareto Front. Overall, the contributions of this work to the MFD-based OTA problem, are:

- Reformulates the OTA problem to generate a representative Pareto frontier using the NBI method. To address the nonconvexity of this problem, this work introduces an approximate linear solution that provides a lower-bound solution to the original nonconvex problem. While this solution may be infeasible, it can be used as a basis to derive efficient, reliable and feasible upper-bound solution.
- Introduces a rolling-horizon algorithmic approach [22] that projects the lower-bound solution into the feasible domain of the original non-convex problem. This projection results in an upper-bound solution.
- Provides an optimization procedure that leverages the Nash bargaining game theory [21] to pinpoint the “optimal” trade-off solution among all the Pareto points.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces the demand and traffic flow models, which are presented in subsections II-A and II-B, respectively. Subsections II-C and II-D mathematically formulate the objective function and the multi-regional OTA problem. Section III describes the Pareto generation procedure for the OTA problem, starting with a presentation of the NBI method in subsection III-A, while subsection III-B proposes a linear formulation of the Pareto generation procedure, which provides a lower bound solution of the original NBI procedure with subsection III-C presenting the proposed rolling-horizon algorithmic approach to identify an upper-bound solution. Furthermore, Section IV-B, mathematically formulates the “knee” and Nash solutions that selects the a good approximated and the “best” trade-off over all generated Pareto points, respectively. Section V evaluates the proposed methodologies, and finally Section VI concludes this work and discusses potential areas for future research.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Demand Model

Let an urban area partitioned into a set of regions, i.e., $\mathcal{R} = \{1, \dots, R\}$ with the sets \mathcal{O} and \mathcal{D} denote the set of regions considered as origins, $\mathcal{O} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ and destinations $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$, respectively. This work assumes that vehicular flows that intent to use the road infrastructure communicate beforehand the time that they desired to arrive at their destination. Let, $d_{od}^D(k)$ denote the number of vehicles traveling from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ to $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and they desire to arrive at d during time-step $k \in \mathcal{K}$, where the set $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ denotes the considered time horizon.

To model demand dynamics we introduce the variables $\tilde{d}_{od}(k)$ and $D_{od}(k)$, representing the *admitted external demand* and *remaining external demand*, from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ to $d \in \mathcal{D}$, during time-step k , respectively. Hence, the admitted external demand denotes the number of vehicles that actually enter o towards d at time-step k , that is limited by the factors of:

- 1) The capacity of the region to serve more vehicles.
- 2) The maximum possible demand that can physically enter region $o \in \mathcal{O}$, defined by the parameter D_o^{MAX} .
- 3) The traffic management scheme that manages the entry rate of vehicles.

Furthermore, the remaining external demand denotes the number of vehicles that are remaining as they are not yet admitted to enter the network. To keep track of the demand that is going to be served during the following time-steps, the dynamics of the remaining external demand at time-step k are mathematically expressed as:

$$D_{od}(k+1) = D_{od}(k) - \tilde{d}_{od}(k), \quad (1)$$

and we make the following assumptions:

- The demand is known beforehand (i.e., $D_{od}(0) = \sum_k d_{od}^D(k)$),
- At the end of the time horizon all the vehicles will be served ($D_{od}(K) = 0$).

B. Traffic Flow Model

The dynamics within each region $r \in \mathcal{R}$ are characterized by the parameters of: the *jam density*, ρ_r^J , *critical density* ρ_r^C , *free-flow speed* u_r^f , *capacity*, $q_r^C = \rho_r^C u_r^f$, *total region length* L_r , *the average trip length* l_r and their ratio $\zeta_r = L_r/l_r$ within region $r \in \mathcal{R}$. The macroscopic modeling framework is complemented by the Macroscopic Fundamental Diagram (MFD) [17] in which the *average flow* $f_r(\rho_r(k))$ veh/h of region r is the product of the region's *density* $\rho_r(k)$ veh/km and *speed* $u_r(\rho_r(k))$ km/h at each time-step k , i.e., $f_r(\rho_r(k)) = \rho_r(k)u_r(\rho_r(k))$. The average flow of a region is derived through the asymmetric unimodal triangular MFD defined as:

$$f_r(\rho_r(k)) = \begin{cases} \frac{q_r^C}{\rho_r^C} \rho_r(k), & \text{if } 0 \leq \rho_r(k) \leq \rho_r^C, \\ w_r(\rho_r^J - \rho_r(k)), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $w_r = q_r^C/(\rho_r^J - \rho_r^C)$ is the congestion propagation speed [17]. Using the average flow we can measure the outflow of a region as follows:

$$q_r(k) = f_r(\rho_r(k))\zeta_r = u_r(\rho_r(k))\rho_r(k)\zeta_r. \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, let variable $\rho_{ord}(k)$ denote the density that currently is in $r \in \mathcal{R}$ that originated from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ destined to $d \in \mathcal{D}$ such that:

$$\rho_r(k) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \rho_{ord}(k). \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the variables $q_{ord}(k)$ and $q_{orjd}(k)$ denote the *transfer flow* originating from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ towards $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and currently in $r \in \mathcal{R}$ and the corresponding flow in region $r \in \mathcal{R}$ originating from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ destined to $d \in \mathcal{D}$ that passes through neighbouring region $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$, respectively, such that:

$$q_{ord}(k) = \frac{q_r(k)}{\rho_r(k)} \rho_{ord}(k) = u_r(\rho_r(k))\rho_{ord}(k)\zeta_r \quad (5)$$

$$q_{ord}(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_r} q_{orjd}(k), \quad (6)$$

$$q_r(k) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} q_{ord}(k). \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{J}_r is defined as

$$\mathcal{J}_r = \begin{cases} \mathcal{J}_r^- \cup \{r\}, & \text{if } r \in \mathcal{D} \\ \mathcal{J}_r^-, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and $\mathcal{J}_r^- \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ is the set of neighboring regions of region $r \in \mathcal{R}$. Interestingly, the amount of flow of vehicles that finish their trip (exit the network) in region $d \in \mathcal{D}$ at time-step k are expressed by the variable $q_{odd}(k)$ as in that case $r = j = d$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$.

Moreover, in macroscopic modeling the maximum flow that can be transferred between neighboring regions $r \in \mathcal{R}$ and $j \in \mathcal{J}_r^-$ is limited by the inter-boundary capacity, $C_{rj}(\rho_j(k))$ which is stated as the maximum transfer flow between two adjacent neighboring regions r and $j \in \mathcal{R}$ as follows:

$$C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) = \begin{cases} C_{rj}^{\text{MAX}}, & \text{if } \rho_j(k) \leq \alpha \rho_j^J, \\ \frac{C_{rj}^{\text{MAX}}}{1 - \alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_j(k)}{\rho_j^J}\right), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where C_{rj}^{MAX} is the maximum inter-boundary capacity and $\alpha \rho_j^J$ is the point where the inter-boundary capacity begins to decline with $0 < \alpha < 1$, [2]. Hence, the *actual transfer flow* from $r \in \mathcal{R}$ to $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$, $\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k)$ is restricted by the remaining capacity of the neighboring regions which is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) = \min \left(q_{orjd}(k), C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) \frac{q_{orjd}(k)}{\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{D}} q_{ory}(k)} \right). \quad (10)$$

Considering all the above, the dynamics of density in region $r \in \mathcal{R}$ that originated from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ towards $d \in \mathcal{D}$, can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{ord}(k+1) &= \rho_{ord}(k) + \frac{1}{L_r} \tilde{d}_{od}(k) \\ &+ \frac{T_s}{L_r} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_r} \left(\tilde{q}_{ojrd}(k) - \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where, T_s denotes the simulation time-step that governs the evolution of dynamics.

C. Objective Function

The multi-regional OTA problem aims to regulate departure times and determine the multi-regional routes for all vehicular flows within the road network. This is done with the goal of minimizing two objectives: (i) the OTA (J_{OTA}), which represents the discrepancy between the time that vehicles desire to arrive and actually arrive at the destination; and (ii) the Total Traveling Time spent (TTT) (J_{TTT}), which represents the total time spent in the network. It should be noted that these two objectives may be conflicting. Achieving the J_{TTT} objective, which is a measure of free-flow traffic conditions, can only be accomplished when there is minimal congestion on the network. However, this goal may conflict with the objective of minimizing the J_{OTA} , particularly when there are numerous drivers attempting to reach the same destination simultaneously. This is exactly the problem during morning and evening peak traffic hours, wherein in such scenarios, it becomes challenging to simultaneously satisfy both objectives, as prioritizing one may come at the expense of the other.

To formally state both objective criteria let variables $S^a(k)$ and $S^b(k)$ represent the cumulative number of vehicles admitted to the network, and successfully arrive at their destination, respectively, such that:

$$S^a(k+1) = S^a(k) + \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{d}_{od}(k), \quad (12)$$

$$S^b(k+1) = S^b(k) + T_s \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{q}_{odd}(k), \quad (13)$$

where $S^a(0) = 0$ and $S^b(0) = 0$. Moreover, let variables $S_{od}^c(k)$ and $S_{od}^d(k)$ represent the cumulative number of vehicles traveling from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ and desire to arrive at $d \in \mathcal{D}$ up-to time-step k , and traveling from $o \in \mathcal{O}$ and actually arriving at $d \in \mathcal{D}$ at time-step k , respectively, such that:

$$S_{od}^c(k+1) = S_{od}^c(k) + d_{od}^D(k), \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (14)$$

$$S_{od}^d(k+1) = S_{od}^d(k) + T_s \tilde{q}_{odd}(k), \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (15)$$

where $S_{od}^c(0) = 0$ and $S_{od}^d(0) = 0$. Using the above definitions, the J_{OTA} objective is expressed as the absolute value of the difference between the cumulative number of vehicles that desire to arrive at $d \in \mathcal{D}$ on or before time-step k , and those that actually arrive on time-step k , over all time-steps, such that:

$$J_{OTA} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} |S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)|. \quad (16)$$

While, the J_{TTT} , is expressed as the sum of the difference between the cumulative number of vehicles admitted to enter the network, and successfully arrive at their destination, over all time-steps, such that:

$$J_{TTT} = \sum_{\mathcal{K}} (S^a(k) - S^b(k)). \quad (17)$$

Finally, the Combined Objective Criterion, (J_{COC}) is defined as the sum of the two above criteria, such that:

$$J_{COC} = J_{OTA} + J_{TTT}. \quad (18)$$

D. Problem Formulation

The OTA problem aims to regulate the admission of vehicles $\tilde{d}_{od}(k)$ and transfer flows $q_{orjd}(k)$ of each region in such a way that the J_{COC} is minimized. The formulation of the OTA problem is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$(P_1) \quad \min J_{COC} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left((S^a(k) - S^b(k)) + \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} |S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)| \right) \quad (19a)$$

s.t. Demand and Traffic Dynamics: (1) – (15),

$$\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{d}_{od}(k) \leq D_o^{MAX}, \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (19b)$$

$$\tilde{d}_{od}(k) \leq D_{od}(k), \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (19c)$$

$$0 \leq \rho_r(k) \leq \rho_r^J, \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, r \in \mathcal{R}, \quad (19d)$$

$$\sum_k d_{od}^D(k) = T_s \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \tilde{q}_{odd}(k), \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (19e)$$

$$D_{od}(K) = 0, \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (19f)$$

$$D_{od}(0) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} d_{od}^D(k), \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, d \in \mathcal{D}. \quad (19g)$$

In problem P_1 , constraints (2) - (15) define the demand and traffic dynamics while constraints (19b) and (19c) sustain the total admitted external demand for all destinations smaller than, the maximum possible external demand, D_o^{MAX} and remaining external demand, $D_{od}(k) \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. Constraint (19d) keeps the density of each region within its physical limits while constraints (19e) and (19f) ensure that all vehicle requests will be served within the considered time horizon. Finally, constraint (19g) ensures that the admitted demand will not surpass the total number of requests. Problem P_1 is a nonconvex nonlinear model since it involves the nonlinear functions Eqs. (2), (9) and (10) a bilinear term of Eq. (5).

III. GENERATION OF THE PARETO FRONT

The OTA problem is a multi-objective optimization problem, where a set of feasible solutions can be obtained by generating the Pareto Front of the J_{COC} objective. In this work, the modified Normal Boundary Intersection (NBI) method proposed in [23] is used to generate a uniformly spread and smooth sample of the Pareto Front. Note that this method can be applied to any general nonlinear multi-objective optimization problem. Despite the fact that NBI is suitable for nonlinear problems the generation of the Pareto is still a challenging task as nonlinear problems cannot be efficiently solved using standard nonlinear solvers. We therefore also propose a solution methodology that generates a feasible Pareto Front based on a convex relaxed problem, which provides a computationally efficient and practical solution to the OTA problem.

A. Normal Boundary Intersection Method For The OTA Problem

To simplify notation, let us denote a feasible solution to problem P_1 by the vector \mathbf{x} . The functions $J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x})$ and $J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x})$ represent the corresponding values of the objectives J_{OTA} and J_{TTT} that can be attained with solution vector \mathbf{x} . Furthermore, let J_{TTT}^* and J_{OTA}^* signify the individual minima of the two objectives of problem P_1 , achieved at \mathbf{x}_{TTT}^* and \mathbf{x}_{OTA}^* , respectively. The individual minimum of each criterion represents the minimum value that each objective can achieve, and the vectors \mathbf{x}_{OTA}^* and \mathbf{x}_{TTT}^* represent their solution such that, $J_{TTT}^* = J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*)$ and $J_{OTA}^* = J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*)$. To encapsulate the cross-evaluation of the objectives at these optimal solutions, we introduce the matrix Φ , a 2×2 matrix defined as:

$$\Phi = \begin{pmatrix} J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*), & J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*) \\ J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*), & J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*) \end{pmatrix}.$$

which encapsulates the values of the objective functions of problem P_1 when evaluated at each other's individual minimum. Moreover, considering that both objective criteria are non-negative, the convex hull of the individual minimum can be defined with the use of the bilinear term $\Phi\beta$, where $\beta = \{(b_1, b_2) | b_1 + b_2 = 1\}$ is a given vector parameter. Then, the NBI method can generate a representative Pareto Front of P_1 by searching for the maximum distance (i.e., t) along the normal pointing toward the origin by solving the following optimization problem,

$$(P_2) \quad \max t \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \Phi\beta + t\hat{n} \geq \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left((S^a(k) - S^b(k)) + \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} |S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)| \right) \quad (20b)$$

Demand and Traffic Dynamics: (1) – (15),
Constraints: (19b) – (19g),

where, $\hat{n} = -\Phi\mathbf{v}^1$ and \mathbf{v} is a vector with strictly positive components (e.g., $\mathbf{v} = (1, 1)^T$). Therefore, a set of uniform distributed Pareto points can be generated by evaluating a set of different equidistant β vectors within the problem P_2 .

B. Linear relaxed Pareto Generation For The OTA Problem

To generate the Pareto Frontier, multiple runs of the nonlinear nonconvex problem of P_2 should be performed. Problem P_2 contains all the nonlinear constraints of P_1 . Thus, obtaining a directed solution for P_2 requires the use of nonlinear solver, which cannot offer real-time execution and optimality guarantees. To solve P_2 efficiently using standard linear solvers, this section proposes a set of linear relaxations to relax P_2 into an approximate convex program.

Let us first consider Eq. (2), which consists of two linear segments that intersect at the critical density that can be relaxed into two linear constraints by replacing the equality sign “=” with inequality “ \leq ” such that:

$$f_r(\rho_r(k)) \leq \frac{q_r^C}{\rho_r^C} \rho_r(k), \quad (21)$$

$$f_r(\rho_r(k)) \leq w_r(\rho_r^J - \rho_r(k)). \quad (22)$$

Note that the combination of the two linear inequalities of Eq. (21) and (22) generate a superset of Eq. (2). Then, considering that the shortest travel times can be achieved only in the case that vehicles are cruising with free-flow speed, then the bilinear term in Eq. (5) can be relaxed by:

$$q_{ord}(k) \leq u_r^f \rho_{ord}(k) \zeta_r. \quad (23)$$

where it is true that $u_r(\rho_r(k)) \leq u_r^f$ for all densities $\rho_r(k)$. Furthermore, Eq. (10) returns the minimum between two functions and can be relaxed as follows:

$$\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \leq q_{orjd}(k) \quad (24)$$

$$\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \leq C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) \frac{q_{orjd}(k)}{\sum_{y \in \mathcal{D}} q_{orjy}(k)}. \quad (25)$$

where Eq. (25) is still nonlinear and it can be further relaxed into a linear function by taking its summation over all $\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k)$ for $d \in \mathcal{D}$ such that:

$$\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \leq C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)). \quad (26)$$

¹The \hat{n} is the normal direction at the point $\Phi\beta$ pointing towards the origin.

Similarly with Eq. (2), Eq. (9) consisted of two linear functions that intersect at the point $a\rho_j^J$ that can be relaxed into two linear constraints by replacing the equality sign “=” with the inequality “ \leq ” such that:

$$C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) \leq C_{rj}^{MAX}, \quad (27)$$

$$C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) \leq \frac{C_{rj}^{MAX}}{1 - \alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_j(k)}{\rho_j^J} \right). \quad (28)$$

Moreover, taking into account the shape of Eq. (9) the maximum transfer flow between two regions can be bounded from above by considering the linear inequality as follows:

$$C_{rj}(\rho_j(k)) \geq \frac{-C_{rj}^{MAX}}{\rho_j^J} (\rho_j(k) - \rho_j^J). \quad (29)$$

Moreover considering the relaxation of Eq. (26) can be combined and handled together with constraints (27)-(29) such that:

$$\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \leq C_{rj}^{MAX}, \quad (30)$$

$$\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \leq \frac{C_{rj}^{MAX}}{1 - \alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_j(k)}{\rho_j^J} \right), \quad (31)$$

$$\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \geq \frac{-C_{rj}^{MAX}}{\rho_j^J} (\rho_j(k) - \rho_j^J), \quad (32)$$

for all $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$. In this way the Eqs. (10) and (9) can be approximated together by the convex envelop consisted of the linear segments of constraints (30)- (32). Finally, the constraint as expressed in (38b), which incorporates an absolute value, can be reformulated into an equivalent linear representation. This is achieved by introducing the slack variable $\psi_{od}(k)$, thereby allowing the replacement of (38b) with the following linear constraints:

$$\Phi\beta + t\hat{n} - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} (S^a(k) - S^b(k)) \geq \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \psi_{od}(k) \right), \quad (33)$$

$$\psi_{od}(k) \geq (S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)), \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, \quad d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (34)$$

$$\psi_{od}(k) \geq -(S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)), \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad o \in \mathcal{O}, \quad d \in \mathcal{D}. \quad (35)$$

Considering all the above relaxations, the problem P_2 can be approximated by a linear program by replacing constraints (2), (5), (9), (10) and (38b) with (21)-(24), (30)-(32) and (33)-(35). Hence, the mathematical formulation of the relaxed version of problem P_2 is given in the problem P_3 as follows:

$$(P_3) \quad \max t \quad (36)$$

s.t. Demand and Traffic Dynamics: (1), (4), (6) – (8),

(11) – (15), (21) – (24), and (30) – (32),

Constraints: (19b) – (19g) and (33) – (35).

The formulation of P_3 is a linear program that offers a relaxed solution of the original nonlinear nonconvex problem

P₂. The resulting relaxation is a lower-bound of the optimal objective value of problem P₂, that may lead to infeasible solutions as may not satisfy some of the original constraints. This is due to the fact that there is a discrepancy between the actual nonlinear problem of P₂ and the approximate solution of P₃. This discrepancy can lead to poor performance and solutions far away from optimality.

C. Feasible Upper-Bound Solution Of The OTA Problem

This work introduces a rolling horizon algorithmic approach to achieve a feasible upper-bound solution, as detailed in Algorithm 1. The algorithm incrementally solves the relaxed version of problem P₃ over predetermined time intervals denoted by M . This procedure is structured into three main steps, each designed to refine the solution progressively and ensure its real-life applicability.

In the first step, the relaxed version of problem P₃ is addressed for the time horizon spanning the steps $k = (M(\eta + 1), \dots, |\mathcal{K}|)$, where η denotes the current interval index. The obtained solution is then projected onto the feasible domain of the original nonconvex problem, P₂. This projection process results in feasible control decisions, favoring the use of split ratios over transfer flows for route guidance. The preference for split ratios is due to their nature as relative measures, which provide a more adaptable and dynamically suitable approach to traffic management under varying conditions. Specifically, the split ratios $\gamma_{orjd}(k) \in [0, 1]$ are defined as:

$$\gamma_{orjd}(k) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{q}_{orjd}(k)}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_r} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k)}, & \text{if } \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_r} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) \neq 0 \\ 1/|\mathcal{J}_r|, & \text{if } \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_r} \tilde{q}_{orjd}(k) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

which proportionally allocate flows to adjacent regions.

The second step assesses the control decisions, namely split ratios and admitted demand, which were determined in the first step. This evaluation employs a macroscopic simulation model, which is built upon the nonlinear dynamics of the Macroscopic Fundamental Diagram (MFD), as detailed in Eqs. (1)-(15). The objective of this step is to refine the quality of the initial solution. Through this process, we derive feasible upper-bound control decisions, specifically $\tilde{d}_{od}^*(k)$ and $\gamma_{orjd}^*(k)$, for the interval $k = (M(\eta+1), \dots, M(\eta+2))$.

The third and final step utilizes the simulated states from the second step to update the initial conditions for all optimization-related variables for subsequent intervals. Thus, in each interval, Algorithm 1 uses the most recent simulated states to refresh the initial conditions for variables such as $\rho_r(k)$, $\rho_{ord}(k)$, $S^a(k)$, $S^b(k)$, $S_{od}^c(k)$, and $S_{od}^d(k)$ for $k = M(\eta+2)$. This rolling horizon update is crucial for ensuring that the initial values of the objective function are accurately propagated to subsequent intervals. Based on the solutions obtained from Step 2 during each iteration, we proceed to update the matrix Φ . This procedure is repeated throughout the entire planning horizon, advancing in increments of M

Algorithm 1 Rolling Horizon Algorithmic Approach

Input: Traffic network parameters: q_r^C , ρ_r^C , ρ_r^J , C_{rj}^{MAX} , $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, α and \mathcal{T} . Demand Profile: $d_{od}^D(k)$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|$.

Initialization: Initialize Φ and set $\rho_r(1) = S^a(1) = S^b(1) = S_{od}^c(1) = S_{od}^d(1) = 0$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$ and $d \in \mathcal{D}$.
for $\eta = 0$ to $\lfloor \frac{|\mathcal{K}|}{M} \rfloor$ **do**

Step 1: Solve problem P₃ and compute the admitted demands $\tilde{d}_{od}(k)$ and split ratios $\gamma_{orjd}(k)$ $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$, $k = (M(\eta + 1), \dots, |\mathcal{K}|)$.

Step 2: Use the non-linear dynamics (1) -(15), to derive state estimates of densities $\rho_r(k)$ and $\rho_{ord}(k)$ and feasible upper bound control decisions, $\tilde{d}_{od}^*(k)$ and γ_{orjd}^* for $k = (M(\eta + 1), \dots, M(\eta + 2))$.

Step 3: Derive the new initial state of all variables of $\rho_r(k)$, $\rho_{ord}(k)$, $S^a(k)$, $S^b(k)$, $S_{od}^c(k)$ and $S_{od}^d(k)$ for $k = M(\eta + 2)$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, and $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and update Φ .
end for

Output: $\tilde{d}_{od}^*(k)$ and $\gamma_{orjd}^*(k)$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}_r$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|$.

time steps and pushing the boundary of the solution space towards feasibility.

IV. METHODS FOR SELECTING A SINGLE PARETO OPTIMAL POINT

A set of uniform distributed Pareto points can be generated by evaluating a set of different equidistant β vectors using the upper-bound feasible solution of Algorithm 1. In doing this, a set of Pareto points will be generated. Each point can be considered as a possible solution (i.e., the Pareto optimal set) where a slight improvement in one objective will degrade the other. The following sections provided two solutions able to provide a unique solution among the Pareto points.

A. Knee Solution

The NBI method can provide a set of Pareto points that accurately represent the entire Pareto surface. To generate this set, multiple equidistant β^* vectors are evaluated within problem P₂. As mentioned previously, the bulge of the Pareto surface at each point is measured by the maximum distance (denoted as t) along the normal pointing towards the origin. Therefore, an efficient solution involves identifying the vector β^* , which corresponds to the “knee” solution of the Pareto front. The “knee” solution represents the point of maximum convex bulge on the Pareto surface of problem P₂. This solution can be identified by solving the following mathematical program:

$$(P_4) \quad \max t \quad (38a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \Phi\beta + t\hat{n} \geq \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left((S^a(k) - S^b(k)) + \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} |S_{od}^c(k) - S_{od}^d(k)| \right) \quad (38b)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
b_1 + b_2 &= 1, \\
b_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } b_2 &\geq 0, \\
\text{Demand and Traffic Dynamics: (1) - (15),} \\
\text{Constraints: (19b) - (19g),}
\end{aligned} \tag{38c}$$

where, b_1 and b_2 are considered as a part of the decisions variables.

B. Nash Pareto Optimal Solution

The ‘‘knee solution’’ provided by the NBI method serves as a reasonable approximation of the optimal solution across all Pareto points. The optimal solution can be identified using the Nash bargaining solution [21], which constitutes one of the solutions that offer an appropriate trade-off among the two objective criteria J_{TTT} and J_{OTA} . Each solution over the Pareto Front is defined by the coordinates $(J_{OTA}^{PF_i}, J_{TTT}^{PF_i})$, where, the superscript PF_i denotes the i^{th} generated point across the Pareto. Accordingly, the Nash bargaining solution is the Pareto point i.e., $(J_{OTA}^{PF*}, J_{TTT}^{PF*})$, that maximizes the total benefit of both objective criteria (J_{TTT} and J_{OTA}). Hence, the Nash bargaining solution is the unique point that maximizes the product of individual net benefit gains from the threat point of the non-cooperative Nash equilibrium. The threat point is defined the worst case solution for each objective function that happens only in case that one objective is optimized without considering the other. Hence, the threat point of Total Traveling Time objective is attained at \mathbf{x}_{OTA}^* where the individual minimum of the OTA objective is achieved i.e., $J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*)$ and in the same manner the threat point of OTA objective is attained at \mathbf{x}_{TTT}^* , i.e., $J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*)$. Considering all the above, the Nash bargaining solution selects the unique solution to the following maximization problem:

$$(\text{P}_5) \quad \max (J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*) - J_{OTA}^{PF})(J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*) - J_{TTT}^{PF}) \tag{39}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{s.t. } J_{OTA}^{PF} &\leq J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*) \\
J_{TTT}^{PF} &\leq J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*).
\end{aligned}$$

The problem P_5 returns the solutions that maximize the product of $(J_{OTA}(\mathbf{x}_{TTT}^*) - J_{OTA}^{PF})(J_{TTT}(\mathbf{x}_{OTA}^*) - J_{TTT}^{PF})$ attained at the single Pareto point \mathbf{x}_{COC}^* . The selected solution is the ‘‘optimal’’ trade-off solution as it minimizes the difference between the actual and the desired arrival time while also reducing the total time spent by all vehicles in the network. Therefore, in order to select a single Pareto optimal solution among all possible solutions Nash solution is obtained by performing a comprehensive analysis of the Pareto Front.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

To evaluate the proposed framework, we considered an urban network consisted of 16 regions in which four regions are considered as origins and four regions are considered as destinations. The traffic dynamics of each region are assumed to follow a triangular MFD model, with parameters: $\rho_r^C = 30$

Fig. 1. The Pareto front generated by applying the NBI method for : (a) the normal and (b) the congested demand scenarios.

veh/km, $\rho_r^J = 130$ veh/km, $L_r = 1$ km, $u_r^f = 60$ km/h, $q_r^C = 1800$ veh/h, $C_{rj}^{\text{MAX}} = 1800$ veh/h and $\alpha = 0.25$. The simulation time-step is selected equal to $T_s = 30$ s while the whole time horizon is set to $\mathcal{T} = 140$ min. Two demand scenarios are considered for evaluation purposes: (i) *normal* scenario with average demand around 2500 veh/h and (ii) *congested* with average demand around 4000 veh/h. The *normal* demand scenario refers to cases where vehicles can be served by the network without causing congestion, while the *congested* scenario refers to cases where congestion would occur without implementing any control policy.

Figures 1 (a) and (b) depict the Pareto Front generated by solving the formulation of P_3 for the normal and congested demand scenarios, respectively. Each scatter in the figures represents a Pareto solution to the approximated formulation of P_3 obtained by evaluating varying values of β ranging between $[0, 1]$. Note that each Pareto solution achieves a different trade-off between the two objective criteria. In particular, both figures depict the two special cases where only one out of the two objectives is optimized by the left- and right-pointing triangles. The left-pointing triangle indicates the case where J_{OTA}^* is minimized, while the right-pointing triangle indicates the case where J_{TTT}^* is minimized. Furthermore, the green rhombus represents the Nash Pareto solution, i.e., J_{COC}^* obtained by solving the P_4 problem, which offers the best trade-off among the two objective criteria. From the figures, we can observe that knee solutions are possible alternative solutions that can offer a good trade-off among the two criteria. On the other hand, we can observe that in the case of congestion, the points around the Nash are sparse, as in the case of congestion, the two conflicting criteria drastically affect each other.

Figures 2 (a), (b), and (c) display the cumulative number

Fig. 2. The cumulative number of vehicles that are admitted to enter the network (Admitted vehicles), complete their trips (Exit vehicles), desire to arrive at their destination (Demand) as a function of time, for the normal demand scenario with: (a) J_{COC}^* ; (b) J_{TTT}^* ; and (c) J_{OTA}^* .

Fig. 3. The cumulative number of vehicles that are admitted to enter the network (Admitted vehicles), complete their trips (Exit vehicles), desire to arrive at their destination (Demand) as a function of time, for the congested demand scenario with: (a) J_{COC}^* ; (b) J_{TTT}^* ; and (c) J_{OTA}^* .

Fig. 4. Evaluation of J_{COC}^* solution in the physical plant in terms of: (a) the cumulative number of vehicles and demand; and (b) the number of exiting vehicles and demand.

of vehicles that have been admitted to enter the network (Admitted vehicles), completed their trips (Exit vehicles), and the number of vehicles that desire to arrive at their destinations (Demand) for the normal demand scenario, using the Pareto solutions of J_{COC}^* , J_{TTT}^* , and J_{OTA}^* , respectively. Similarly, Figures 3 (a), (b), and (c) show the same findings for the congested demand scenario, again using the Pareto solutions of J_{COC}^* , J_{TTT}^* , and J_{OTA}^* , respectively. The comparison of the results in both Figures 2 (c) and 3 (c) reveals that the J_{OTA}^* solution outperforms in terms of the number of vehicles that arrive at their destination on-time, but it has the poorest performance in terms of travel times reductions. Conversely, Figure 2 (b) shows that J_{TTT}^* provides better performance in terms of travel time savings but has the worst performance according to the OTA criterion. This distinction becomes more evident when considering the congested demand scenario in Figure 3 (b), where an increase in demand results in the need to compromise the arrival times of some vehicles to maintain short travel times. Moreover, Figure 2 (a) and Figure 3 (a) indicate that for both demand scenarios,

the J_{COC}^* solution offers a balanced trade-off between the two criteria by providing significant travel time savings while also accommodating the majority of vehicles to arrive on-time.

Finally, to evaluate the derived control actions under realistic conditions, we utilize the modeling framework of Sections II-A and II-B to develop a macroscopic simulation framework that acts as the physical plant. In this framework, we evaluate the quality of the upper-bound solution proposed in Section III-C by applying the control decisions obtained through the Nash Pareto solution, J_{COC}^* considering the normal demand scenario. Figs. 4 (a) and (b) show the cumulative number and the number of vehicles that complete their trips considering the solution of both lower bound (Exit vehicles) and upper bound (Exit vehicles simulator) approaches, respectively. Both figures show a strong alignment between the lower and upper-bound solutions, with all vehicles arriving at the destination almost simultaneously and travel times remaining consistently low.

Optimality Gap: The quality of the solutions obtained from the feasible upper-bound solution is compared in terms of the optimality gap with the solution derived directly from the “knee” solution (lower-bound solution) without involving Algorithm 1. Specifically, the *optimality gap* is defined as:

$$\text{Optimality Gap} = \frac{J_{COC}^{\text{Alg}} - J_{COC}^{\text{LB}}}{J_{COC}^{\text{LB}}} \times 100\%,$$

where J_{COC}^{LB} denotes the lower-bound objective value obtained from the solution of Problem P_4 over the entire time horizon, $T = 140$ time-steps. Meanwhile, J_{COC}^{Alg} denotes the objective value obtained by creating a feasible solution through Algorithm 1. Table I presents the optimality gap considering various demand scenarios. The results show that the proposed solution can achieve results close to optimality,

Optimality Gap				
Scenario 1 7000 veh/h	Scenario 2 55000 veh/h	Scenario 3 4000 veh/h	Scenario 4 3000 veh/h	Scenario 5 2000 veh/h
15.8%	14.8%	15.6%	15.7%	15.1%

TABLE I
OPTIMALITY GAP OF “KNEE” SOLUTION (LOWER-BOUND) AND THE
FEASIBLE UPPER-BOUND SOLUTION.

as the gap between the lower and upper bound solutions is at most 15.8%.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a novel demand management scheme to alleviate traffic congestion by managing vehicular flow departure times and regional routes to follow. To do so this work presents the OTA problem that results in a nonconvex nonlinear multi-objective optimization program. An efficient solution is obtained through a convex relaxation method in which the NBI method is employed to generate a representative Pareto Front. Finally, the “knee” and the Nash bargain solutions are used to select the best Pareto solution that can drastically reduce the travel times and guarantee that all vehicles arrive at the destination as close as possible to their desired time.

Future work will explore the development of a solution approach that can provide a single knee solution without generating all the Pareto points. Additionally, the current approach assumes that demand is known in advance, so future research will focus on developing a robust approach that can anticipate uncertainties in demand distributions.

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